

National ASTER Map of Australia

Organization	GO FAIR
Created by	National Computational Infrastructure (NCI Australia) (datacollections.nci@anu.edu.au)
Based on	FIP Wizard 3, 3.0.17 (gofair:fip-wizard-3:3.0.17)
Project Phase	Defining FAIR Implementation Profile
Project Tags	Type: FIP
Description	<p>This FAIR Implementation Profile (FIP) describes the National ASTER Map of Australia (https://dx.doi.org/10.25914/5f224f36ec890) published by the National Computational Infrastructure (NCI). It outlines the FAIR implementation choices implemented for each of the FAIR Principles. The FIP is available in different human-readable and machine-actionable formats (e.g. CSV, JSON, PDF).</p>
Created at	27 Jul 2023

I. About

Questions

No questions

II. Declare your FAIR Implementation Community

Questions

1

Select your FAIR Implementation Community

Geophysics 2030 | <https://doi.org/10.47486/XN002>

2

Who is the Community Data Steward?

National Computational Infrastructure | <https://ror.org/04yx6dh41>

3

Specify the start date for the validity of the FIP

2023-07-28

4

Specify the end date for the validity of the FIP

2050-12-31

III. Declarations for Findability

Questions

1

Declaration F1 Metadata: What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

DOI | Digital Object Identifier

The digital object identifier (DOI) system originated in a joint initiative of three trade associations in the publishing industry (International Publishers Association; International Association of Scientific, Technical and Medical Publishers; Association of American Publishers). The system was announced at the Frankfurt Book Fair 1997. The International DOI Foundation (IDF) was created to develop and manage the DOI system, also in 1997. The DOI system was adopted as International Standard ISO 26324 in 2012. The DOI system implements the Handle System and adds a number of new features. The DOI system provides an infrastructure for persistent unique identification of objects of any type. The DOI system is designed to work over the Internet. A DOI name is permanently assigned to an object to provide a resolvable persistent network link to current information about that object, including where the object, or information about it, can be found on the Internet. While information about an object can change over time, its DOI name will not change. A DOI name can be resolved within the DOI system to values of one or more types of data relating to the object identified by that DOI name, such as a URL, an e-mail address, other identifiers and descriptive metadata. The DOI system enables the construction of automated services and transactions. Applications of the DOI system include but are not limited to managing information and documentation location and access; managing metadata; facilitating electronic transactions; persistent unique identification of any form of any data; and commercial and non-commercial transactions. The content of an object associated with a DOI name is described unambiguously by DOI metadata, based on a structured extensible data model that enables the object to be associated with metadata of any desired degree of precision and granularity to support description and services. The data model supports interoperability between DOI applications. The scope of the DOI system is not defined by reference to the type of content (format, etc.) of the referent, but by reference to

the functionalities it provides and the context of use. The DOI system provides, within networks of DOI applications, for unique identification, persistence, resolution, metadata and semantic interoperability.

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RAnAWGdel_1GGmDAqv-vZjby5XqbL2ZujNz1vgwK_6cRI#DOI

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2

Declaration F1 Data: What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for datasets?

- b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

The digital object identifier (DOI) system originated in a joint initiative of three trade associations in the publishing industry (International Publishers Association; International Association of Scientific, Technical and Medical Publishers; Association of American Publishers). The system was announced at the Frankfurt Book Fair 1997. The International DOI Foundation (IDF) was created to develop and manage the DOI system, also in 1997. The DOI system was adopted as International Standard ISO 26324 in 2012. The DOI system implements the Handle System and adds a number of new features. The DOI system provides an infrastructure for persistent unique identification of objects of any type. The DOI system is designed to work over the Internet. A DOI name is permanently assigned to an object to provide a resolvable persistent network link to current information about that object, including where the object, or information about it, can be found on the Internet. While information about an object can change over time, its DOI name will not change. A DOI name can be resolved within the DOI system to values of one or more types of data relating to the object identified by that DOI name, such as a URL, an e-mail address, other identifiers and descriptive metadata. The DOI system enables the construction of automated services and transactions. Applications of the DOI system include but are not limited to managing information and documentation location and access; managing metadata; facilitating electronic transactions; persistent unique identification of any form of any data; and commercial and non-commercial transactions. The content of an object associated with a DOI name is described unambiguously by DOI metadata, based on a structured extensible data model that enables the object to be associated with metadata of any desired degree of precision and granularity to support description and services. The data model supports interoperability between DOI applications. The scope of the DOI system is not defined by reference to the type of content (format, etc.) of the referent, but by reference to the functionalities it provides and the context of use. The DOI system provides, within networks of DOI applications, for unique identification, persistence, resolution, metadata and semantic interoperability.

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RAnAWGdel_1GGmDAQv-vZjby5XqbL2ZujNz1vgwK_6cRI#DOI

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

3

Declaration F2: What metadata schema do you use for findability?

- ✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

3.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

3.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

ISO 19115 | Geographic information - Metadata

ISO 19115 defines the schema required for describing geographic information and services by means of metadata. It provides information about the identification, the extent, the quality, the spatial and temporal aspects, the content, the spatial reference, the portrayal, distribution, and other properties of digital geographic data and services.

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RAw8X2gfKkN6Df_Wws3Axou4vMrejVEFumgga52D_i1nY#ISO_19115

3.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

4

Declaration F3: What is the schema that links the persistent identifiers of your data to the metadata description?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

4.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

4.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

DOI | Digital Object Identifier

The digital object identifier (DOI) system originated in a joint initiative of three trade associations in the publishing industry (International Publishers Association; International Association of Scientific, Technical and Medical Publishers; Association of American Publishers). The system was announced at the Frankfurt Book Fair 1997. The International DOI Foundation (IDF) was created to develop and manage the DOI system, also in 1997. The DOI system was adopted as International Standard ISO 26324 in 2012. The DOI system implements the Handle System and adds a number of new features. The DOI system provides an infrastructure for persistent unique identification of objects of any type. The DOI system is designed to work over the Internet. A DOI name is permanently assigned to an object to provide a resolvable persistent network link to current information about that object, including where the object, or information about it, can be found on the Internet. While information about an object can change over time, its DOI name will not change. A DOI name can be resolved within the DOI system to values of one or more types of data relating to the object identified by that DOI name, such as a URL, an e-mail address, other identifiers and descriptive metadata. The DOI system enables the construction of automated services and transactions. Applications of the DOI system include but are not limited to managing information and documentation location and access; managing metadata; facilitating electronic transactions; persistent unique identification of any form of any data; and commercial and non-commercial transactions. The content of an object associated with a DOI name is described unambiguously by DOI metadata, based on a structured extensible data model that enables the object to be associated with metadata of any desired degree of precision and granularity to support description and services. The data model supports interoperability between DOI applications. The scope of the DOI system is not defined by reference to the type of content (format, etc.) of the referent, but by reference to the functionalities it provides and the context of use. The DOI system provides, within networks of DOI applications, for unique identification, persistence, resolution, metadata and semantic interoperability.

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RAnAWGdel_1GGmDAqv-vZjby5XqbL2ZujNz1vgwK_6cRI#DOI

4.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

5

Declaration F4 Metadata: Which service do you use to publish your metadata records?

- ✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

5.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

5.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

GeoNetwork

GeoNetwork is a catalog application to manage spatially referenced resources. It provides powerful metadata editing and search functions as well as an interactive web map viewer. It is currently used in numerous Spatial Data Infrastructure initiatives across the world.

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RAUbP_FvGrwsW3MAWbrkfy0rnvjTpNrX41S2tl1xOb_EU#GeoNetwork

5.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

5.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DataCite | DataCite Ontology

The DataCite Ontology (DataCite) is an ontology that enables the metadata properties of the DataCite Metadata Schema Specification (i.e., a list of metadata properties for the accurate and consistent identification of a resource for citation and retrieval purposes) to be described in RDF.

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RANGw57Qlx5BklwMWCP1srqv4KG1o1I8cvA2IRaHq_HDg#DataCite

5.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

6

Declaration F4 Datasets: Which service do you use to publish your datasets?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

6.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

6.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

TDS | THREDDS Data Server | <https://gcmd.earthdata.nasa.gov/kms/concept/77cae7cb-4676-4c69-a88b-d78971496f97>

6.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

6.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

IV. Declarations for Accessibility

Questions

1

Declaration A1.1 Metadata: Which standardized communication protocol do you use for metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

HTTPS | Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure

Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS) is an extension of the Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP). It is used for secure communication over a computer network, and is widely used on the Internet. In HTTPS, the communication protocol is encrypted using Transport Layer Security (TLS) or, formerly, Secure Sockets Layer (SSL). The protocol is therefore also referred to as HTTP over TLS, or HTTP over SSL

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RAF1ANn-BCFop0OBMOC7S8NtG0y_xYhRX4tAu37XZVCo0#HTTPS

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

1.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

OAI-PMH Schema | Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting Schema

The Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting Schema (OAI-PMH Schema) provides a formal structure for validating responses as part of the OAI-PMH Protocol. The OAI-PMH Protocol is a low-barrier mechanism for repository interoperability. Data Providers are repositories that expose structured metadata via OAI-PMH. Service Providers then make OAI-PMH service requests to harvest that metadata. OAI-PMH is a set of six verbs or services that are invoked within HTTP.

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RAnwFn9lcKK8S2tccnwPZJw-0_hF5N03BL-8BuchPHtvQ#OAI-PMH

1.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✔ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

1.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

CSW | Catalog Service for the Web

Catalogue services support the ability to publish and search collections of descriptive information (metadata) for data, services, and related information objects. Metadata in catalogues represent resource characteristics that can be queried and presented for evaluation and further processing by both humans and software. Catalogue services are required to support the discovery and binding to registered information resources within an information community.

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RA9SQLjEkTvq9qgaHU_IdN0ntL9gYgi0Tu_55ZOr4eMf4#CSW

1.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

This question has not been answered yet!

2

Declaration A1.1 Datasets: Which standardized communication protocol do you use for datasets?

- b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

HTTPS | Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure

Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS) is an extension of the Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP). It is used for secure communication over a computer network, and is widely used on the Internet. In HTTPS, the communication protocol is encrypted using Transport Layer Security (TLS) or, formerly, Secure Sockets Layer (SSL). The protocol is therefore also referred to as HTTP over TLS, or HTTP over SSL

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RAF1ANn-BCFop0OBMOC7S8NtG0y_xYhRX4tAu37XZVCo0#HTTPS

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

OPeNDAP | Open-source Project for a Network Data Access Protocol

OPeNDAP is a protocol that provides a discipline-neutral means of requesting and providing data across

the World Wide Web.

- [See more here](#)

<http://purl.org/np/RApihvFKR8-JO6eD5nuYMkyEDONbIZZC5uDkjdqqq0ZQ#OPeNDAP>

2.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

WCS | Web Coverage Service

A WCS offers multi-dimensional coverage data for access over the Internet.

- [See more here](#)

<http://purl.org/np/RADEkw5zxPhYxu2g31KjA8Xi9ODUzKsnLkNM-vBg7RMX0#WCS>

2.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

- ✓ Also available via NCI's GSKY Service: <https://dx.doi.org/10.25914/608bfc00a6be2>

2.b.1.d.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

WMS | Web Map Service

The OpenGIS Web Map Service Interface Standard (WMS) provides a simple HTTP interface for requesting geo-registered map images from one or more distributed geospatial databases.

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RAFO4Lu8kp5j6xTN5MZ3qRLO_yZkGCuefm0dzboWA9Ygo#WMS

2.b.1.d.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.d.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

- ✓ Also available via NCI's GSKY Service: <https://dx.doi.org/10.25914/608bfc00a6be2>

2.b.1.e.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

2.b.1.e.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.e.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

This question has not been answered yet!

2.b.1.f.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

NCML | NetCDF Markup Language | <http://www.unidata.ucar.edu/namespaces/netcdf/ncml-2.2>

2.b.1.f.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.f.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

This question has not been answered yet!

2.b.1.g.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

UDDC | Unidata Attribute Convention for Data Discovery | <https://docs.unidata.ucar.edu/netcdf-java/4.6/userguide/metadata/DataDiscoveryAttConvention.html>

2.b.1.g.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.g.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

 This question has not been answered yet!

3

Declaration A1.2 Metadata: Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for metadata records?

- b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

3.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

3.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Open Data

practice of sharing data publicly and reusably

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RA63-_ZV5MsUMBGvOTpqpgg3rxn7dSkHD8HOq4f2cdyvc#OPENDATA

3.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

This question has not been answered yet!

4

Declaration A1.2 Datasets: Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for datasets?

- b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

4.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

4.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

HTTPS | Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure

Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS) is an extension of the Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP). It is used for secure communication over a computer network, and is widely used on the Internet. In HTTPS, the communication protocol is encrypted using Transport Layer Security (TLS) or, formerly, Secure Sockets Layer (SSL). The protocol is therefore also referred to as HTTP over TLS, or HTTP over SSL

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RAF1ANn-BCFop0OBMOC7S8NtG0y_xYhRX4tAu37XZVCo0#HTTPS

4.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

- ✓ <https://my.nci.org.au/mancini/signup/>

5

Declaration A2: What metadata preservation policy do you use?

- ✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

5.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

5.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DataCite DOI Policy

DataCite is providing metadata informations through its DOI oriented service. This allows to give information about DOI related preservation policy

- [See more here](#)

<http://purl.org/np/RA4rdLbzwrBDZzdVLVophtrDEQVvevzou3dihHRZzH4o#datacite-doi-policy>

5.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

V. Declarations for Interoperability

Questions

1

Declaration I1 Metadata: What knowledge representation language (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

HTML: The HyperText Markup Language

The HyperText Markup Language or HTML is the standard markup language for documents designed to be displayed in a web browser. It is often assisted by technologies such as Cascading Style Sheets (CSS) and scripting languages such as JavaScript. Web browsers receive HTML documents from a web server or from local storage and render the documents into multimedia web pages. HTML describes the structure of a web page semantically and originally included cues for its appearance.

- [See more here](#)

<http://purl.org/np/RAVoliicDuWm0TCWvcpXIo5PoA7RdCv8WVDwdtYUuAEVc#HTML>

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

1.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

XMLS | eXtensible Markup Language Schema

XMLS defines and describes a class of XML documents by using schema components to constrain and document the meaning, usage and relationships of their constituent parts: datatypes, elements and their content and attributes and their values.

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RA5E0NA_BAilxwHhZKQm-ltnF0xw3ateI8UFxZ0rs8N5Q#XML_Schema

1.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

1.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

RDF | Resource Description Framework

The Resource Description Framework (RDF) is a framework for representing information in the Web.

- [See more here](#)

<http://purl.org/np/RAutRQwoS4d5eLq7eBV1xsnWZ2spDYH4xfhhRzOxSZdhs#RDF>

1.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

1.b.1.d.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Portable Document Format (PDF)

The Portable Document Format (PDF), standardized as ISO 32000, is a file format developed by Adobe in 1992 to present documents, including text formatting and images, in a manner independent of application software, hardware, and operating systems. Based on the PostScript language, each PDF file encapsulates a complete description of a fixed-layout flat document, including the text, fonts, vector graphics, raster images and other information needed to display it.

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RAuxR5Gx_uvVBoePV226Lk86VRYrh9EpmqFXU7f_oojQ#pdf

1.b.1.d.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.d.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2

Declaration I1 Datasets: What knowledge representation language (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for datasets?

- ✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

NetCDF | Network Common Data Form

Unidata's Network Common Data Form (netCDF) is a set of software libraries and a machine-independent data format that support the creation, access, and sharing of array-oriented scientific data. This record describes the data format and not the software libraries. The netCDF Data Model is also a community standard for sharing scientific data. The data model of dimensions, variables, and attributes, which define the The Classic Model, was extended starting with netCDF-4.0. The new The Enhanced Data Model supports the classic model in a completely backward-compatible way, while allowing access to new features such as groups, multiple unlimited dimensions, and new types, including user-defined types. For maximum interoperability with existing code, new data should be created with the The Classic

Model. The Classic Model was introduced with the very first netCDF release, and is still the core of all netCDF files.

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RAdLEtlqBBprmFUyN3rnpq_30o8G35R95_YqNYEdKmX6M#NetCDF

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

3

Declaration I2 Metadata: What structured vocabulary do you use to annotate your metadata records?

- ✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

3.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

3.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

ABS 1297.0 | Australian and New Zealand Standard Research Classification (ANZSRC), 2008 |

<http://purl.org/au-research/vocabulary/anzsrc-for/2008/>

3.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- b. Currently in use, but is planned to be replaced in the future

3.b.1.a.2.b.1

Select the replacement FAIR Enabling Resource

1297.0 ANZSRC | Australian and New Zealand Standard Research Classification, 2020: Fields of Research (FoR) | <https://linked.data.gov.au/def/anzsrc-for/2020/>

3.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

This question has not been answered yet!

4

Declaration I2 Datasets: What structured vocabulary do you use to encode your datasets

- a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

4.a.1

Considerations (optional)

This question has not been answered yet!

5

Declaration I3 Metadata: What semantic model do you use for your metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

5.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

5.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

ISO 19115 | Geographic information - Metadata

ISO 19115 defines the schema required for describing geographic information and services by means of metadata. It provides information about the identification, the extent, the quality, the spatial and temporal aspects, the content, the spatial reference, the portrayal, distribution, and other properties of digital geographic data and services.

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RAw8X2gfKkN6Df_Wws3Axou4vMrejVEFumgga52D_i1nY#ISO_19115

5.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

6

Declaration I3 Datasets: What semantic model do you use for your datasets?

- ✓ a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

6.a.1

Considerations (optional)

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

VI. Declarations for Reusability

Questions

1

Declaration R1.1 Metadata: Which usage license do you use for your metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

CC BY 4.0 | Attribution 4.0 International

Using this licence you are free to share and adapt the resource but you must give appropriate credit.

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RAQ_sGdY_Qc711O_zmn4nr-pMBOxKU04Ur9s998rS6Fc#CC-BY-4.0

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✘ This question has not been answered yet!

2

Declaration R1.1 Datasets: Which usage license do you use for your datasets?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

CC BY 4.0 | Attribution 4.0 International

Using this licence you are free to share and adapt the resource but you must give appropriate credit.

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RAQ_sGdY_Qc7I1O_zmn4nr-pMBOxKU04Ur9s998rS6Fc#CC-BY-4.0

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

✘ This question has not been answered yet!

3

Declaration R1.2 Metadata: What metadata schema do you use for describing the provenance of your metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

3.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

3.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

ISO 19115 | Geographic information - Metadata

ISO 19115 defines the schema required for describing geographic information and services by means of metadata. It provides information about the identification, the extent, the quality, the spatial and temporal aspects, the content, the spatial reference, the portrayal, distribution, and other properties of digital geographic data and services.

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RAw8X2gfKkN6Df_Wws3Axou4vMrejVEFumgga52D_i1nY#ISO_19115

3.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

- ✓ Where relevant, metadata provenance information is recorded as part of the ISO 19115 "resourceSpecificUsage", including "Source provider", "Source ID", "Last harvest" and "Source link".

4

Declaration R1.2 Datasets: What metadata schema do you use for describing the provenance of your datasets?

- ✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

4.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

4.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

ISO 19115 | Geographic information - Metadata

ISO 19115 defines the schema required for describing geographic information and services by means of metadata. It provides information about the identification, the extent, the quality, the spatial and temporal aspects, the content, the spatial reference, the portrayal, distribution, and other properties of digital geographic data and services.

- [See more here](#)

http://purl.org/np/RAw8X2gfKkN6Df_Wws3Axou4vMrejVEFumgga52D_i1nY#ISO_19115

4.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration (optional)

- ✓ Where relevant, data provenance information is recorded as part of the ISO 19115 "Resource Lineage".

5

Declaration R1.3: Your community uses this FAIR Implementation Profile to link to domain-relevant community standards. Please acknowledge this statement by clicking on 'Read and understood'.

- ✓ a. Read and understood.

VII. Register a new resource as a nanopublication

Questions

No questions